

Development of Proof Skills in Abstract Algebra Through Learning Communities

Desenvolvimento de Habilidades de Prova em Álgebra Abstrata por Meio de Comunidades de Aprendizagem

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Abstract

The work of a professional mathematician can be emulated in the classroom by working in learning communities and thus, seeking an environment conducive to interaction, discussion and review between students and the teacher. Skills such as mathematical proof can be benefited in these environments, since the revision, strengthening, validation and refutation of logical processes are presented in these communities and are essential in the mathematical proof processes. In this research, a university course in abstract algebra was structured to promote the work of students in learning communities and the proof schemes presented individually and in groups were analyzed. These schemes were classified as external, empirical, and analytical, and the influence of collective work was described as an enhancer of the progress of the mathematical proof process. This type of learning community structure can be considered as an efficient alternative for the development of proof skills in university students, since in this way opportunities are generated for continuous interaction, contrasting and refutation of results.

Keywords: Mathematical Proof. Learning Communities. Proofs Schemes. Abstract Algebra.

Resumo

O trabalho de um matemático profissional pode ser imitado em sala de aula trabalhando em comunidades de aprendizagem e, assim, buscando um ambiente propício à interação, discussão e revisão entre alunos e professor. Habilidades como prova matemática podem ser beneficiadas nesses ambientes, uma vez que a revisão, reforço, validação e refutação de processos lógicos são apresentados nessas comunidades e são essenciais nos processos de prova matemática. Nesta pesquisa, um curso universitário de álgebra abstrata foi estruturado para promover o trabalho dos alunos em comunidades de aprendizagem e os esquemas de prova apresentados individualmente e em grupos foram analisados. Esses esquemas foram classificados como externos, empíricos e analíticos, e a influência do trabalho coletivo foi descrita como potencializadora do andamento do processo de prova matemática. Esse tipo de estrutura de comunidade de aprendizagem pode ser considerada uma alternativa eficiente para o desenvolvimento de habilidades de prova em estudantes universitários, pois dessa forma são geradas oportunidades de interação contínua, contraste e refutação de resultados.

Palavras-chave: Prova Matemática. Comunidades de Aprendizagem. Esquemas de Provas. Álgebra abstrata.

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1. Introduction

Learning in mathematics is related to the work done by a mathematician by profession, in the sense that learners work with problems and questions that are new to them and perform similar activities of exploration, conjecture, analysis, interpretation, deduction and verification of results (Rodríguez, 2019). In addition, work in this area of science is rarely done individually, it is usually done at least in pairs or groups, and the recognition of this depends on validation by an academic community. This collective process can be emulated in the classroom, creating learning communities in which students share, explore, and validate or refute their results with each other and with other members of the academic community.

In the Communities of mathematicians, actions such as contrasting, studying and verifying the results, not only gives validity to their approaches and results, but also gives confidence to those who do them and motivates the subject to continue with his work. Confidence also positively influences the development of individuals' mathematical thinking (Cretchley, 2008; Shaw Pogossian & Ramirez, 2020), which makes sense to offer Opportunities To promote the recognition of the student by their peers, the distinctions on the part of the experts, and the study, verification and acceptance or refutation of their approaches by the expert community.

In particular, in the training of mathematicians and teachers specialized in this area, formal proof stands out as a process of great importance, since it requires a deep understanding of the mathematical concepts involved, their interrelationships and interactions and good deductive logical reasoning (Tall, 2002; Hanna, 2000). Therefore, for teaching it is necessary to join forces to encourage students to develop the skills necessary to satisfactorily apply the proof processes. However, being a process of extreme complexity there are usually many difficulties in their learning linked, on the one hand, with the cognitive to logical and symbolic formalism,

abstraction and the structure of the proof; and on the other, with the affective, to the beliefs that individuals have about the difficulty in the argumentative process, the confidence of the students and the lack of opportunities to reflect on their mistakes (Güler, 2016).

This research presents a proposal for the development of these proof skills by university students, based on the creation of learning communities in the classroom, to emulate the work of a mathematician by profession, to favor student interactions, guide joint work, who can share their knowledge, procedures and statements, seeking with this that they are reviewed in groups, evaluated, validated or refuted, and thus progress in their way of demonstrating.

2. Literature Review

The influence of collaborative work in the form of learning communities has been studied in a myriad of proposals. Such is the case of Brodie (2020), who worked with teachers on improving teaching practices to optimize their students' understanding and engagement in mathematics; Little (2020) who did it to improve the math achievements of high school students, focusing on beliefs; and, Campbell and Lee (2017) who sought to reinforce mathematical knowledge for the teaching of secondary school teachers.

As for the development of skills to demonstrate, work in learning communities has been relegated to the background. With the exception of works such as that of Bleiler-Baxter and Pair (2017), in which they consider that learning mathematics can be seen as an advance where the sociocultural environment participates fully; It has commonly been considered that this skill is developed individually, that the key point in the development of this is in the continuous reflection of the student and, therefore, the praxis exercised in classes where these themes are oriented focuses on solo work (Hanna & Jahnke, 1996; Segal, 1999; Lehrer & Lesh, 2013; Minggi, Mulabar & Assagaf, 2021).

This fact becomes more evident when working with abstract algebra, since the

abstraction and formality proper to this branch is rarely considered in literature. There are few works like Hausberger (2015) or Gallian (2021), which take up these aspects and consider the level of complexity of the reflection that students must make to understand this subject. That is why this research sought to clarify the behavior of students when making proofs in abstract algebra, particularly considering it as a community process, describe the characteristics that underlie this social construction of the process and observe how these skills develop in the learner.

3. Theoretical Background

3.1. Learning Communities

For this study, learning communities were considered as part of the communities of practice described by Wenger (1999), for whom, in essence, these communities are made up of a group of people gathered around certain common interests; People learn through interaction with each other, sharing their knowledge, tools, plans and solutions.

In particular, when learning mathematics, the constitution of these learning communities can generate an environment that favors the formation of the individual, however, the structure and purposes of said organization must be properly defined to ensure the benefits of this organization (Riscanevo-Espitia, 2016). As has been described, the intention of the formation of these communities is the emulation of the work of a mathematician by profession. The generation of spaces to share knowledge, evaluate approaches, review peers and validate or reject results.

The structure of the learning community built for this research It was defined according to the following roles: coordinator, who organizes activities, connects community

members and contributes to maintaining the community's focus on interests; the core, consisting of members actively involved in the development of activities; and peripheral members who Observed the interactions of core members (Wenger, McDermott and Snyder, 2002). These roles oversaw the course teacher, the students of the course, and Some teachers Members of the bachelor's program.

It is also worth mentioning that the aspects described by Bandura (1976) regarding the theory of social learning were considered. That is, in general terms, both the internal and external factors that influence the student's development and variables to be controlled were considered. This is reflected in the structure of the community (the roles), the emotional and belief aspects analyzed, and in the contextual academic considerations that were taken when raising the proof statements.

3.2. Mathematical proofs

To determine the development of skills in mathematical proof, the processes made by a group of students were analyzed, based on the three mathematical proof schemes proposed by Harel and Sowder (1998), which allow us to understand the level of reasoning and understanding of the subject who performs the proof.

A proof scheme is all the arguments that are necessary for an individual to convince himself or herself or to persuade a person or community of the validity of a result or statement (Harel and Sowder, 2007). The source, organization, quality of speech and reasoning that accompany the process, define the level of proof scheme in external, empirical and analytical, which represent different cognitive stages in the mathematical development of the student.

Table 1.
Description of Proof Schemes.

Schema Type	Description
External Schemas	They can be characterized as authoritarian proofs, those that the individual accepts because they appear in books, or because they are made by professors or other

	students that they consider intellectually superior; ritual proofs, based on opinions or the form of the proof, regardless of the content; and symbolic, in which the student tries to convince through the use of representations and symbolic statements, even if he does not know their meaning (Sowder & Harel, 1998).
Empirical Schemes	Proofs can be inductive, which are those they perform based on examples or their preconceptions (which may be wrong); or intuitive, making deductions based on their sensory perceptions about the approach, observation of patterns or substitution in formulas, which seems correct to them and therefore must be validated without further arguments (Harel & Sowder, 2007).
Analytical Schemes	They are those in which the validation of a hypothesis or approach is presented by means of logical deduction. The proof is based on definitions with formal structures and the concepts used are developed through logical-deductive arguments (Harel & Sowder, 1998). The student achieves verification using axioms and understands the difference between an axiom and a theorem (Ceylan & Güler, 2015). The analytical schemes are of two types: transformational when the student makes mental conjectures related to the proposition to be demonstrated and makes deductions based on his conjectures, generalizes and evidence operability and logical deduction; or axiomatic when the central axis of the process is based on the use of axioms or theorems.

4. Methodological Aspects

We worked with university students of the teacher training program of Bachelor of Mathematics. There were twelve individuals, whose ages range from 18 to 21 years. The research was developed during a university semester (about 16 weeks), with an intensity of five hours a week. Due to social isolation due to the pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus (COVID-19), the activities were developed during virtual meetings (synchronous and asynchronous) using Google's Meet platform.

A system of six activities was proposed whose priority was the proof of abstract algebra propositions and in which the following themes were included: Proof Methods, Equivalence Relations, Groups and Subgroups, Cyclic Groups, Lateral Classes, and Group Homomorphisms. These activities were presented to students through a simple instructional design that focused attention on community work.

In general terms, participants were encouraged to analyze the proposed statements, suggesting that they focus on interpreting the proposition, identify the hypothesis, the thesis, and the elements that they would need to know to build the proof. Subsequently, they were asked to individually and intuitively and without formalities sketch a

method of proof, to make simple statements, to consider whether it could be demonstrated directly, some indirect process, whether mathematical induction was required, or some refutation by counterexample.

They were then asked to organize three-member teams and with them discuss the process and then formally conduct the proof. The team would then present it to the rest of the group for discussion and discussion. At the end of the session, each student was asked for a handwritten document where the proofs made were collected, the logic of each step was argued, and the process was described.

These documents were evaluated by the professor, who focused on refuting the claims, pointing out suggestions and strengthening the proofs if required. In the next class, the corrections were socialized to the students in front of the group in general, without exposing the authorship of each work, and the meeting was invited again, so that the original teams presented a final document with the proofs.

5. Emerging Proof Schemes in Student Work in Learning Communities

To describe the proof schemes that emerged from the students' work in the learning communities, some examples of the answers offered by the participants divided by theme are

presented. For each one, the statement is established, the answers are analyzed, and the demonstrative scheme is characterized.

5.1. Activity: Proof methods

This activity was carried out in the second week of classes. The objective was to analyze the

students' preconceptions to the course and their performance in the proof of theorems. The proposition was proposed: Show that the real numbers a and b are roots of the quadratic equation $ax^2 + px + q = 0$, if and only if, $a + b = -p$ and $ab = q$. Figure 1 shows a proof of this statement by one of the students.

Figure 1.

Act1-1 External Conviction Demonstration Scheme.

It is observed that, without justifying or offering details, the student wants to demonstrate the sufficiency of the proposition. The same situation is observed at the end when you want to test the need. When the student is asked about his answer, he states that "I write what I understand [...] According to what I researched [...] I found a problem with a similar statement and from there I was guided."(→)

With the above, this solution can be categorized in the scheme of external conviction proposed by Harel & Sowder (1988), because the student is convinced by what is observed in books or by what another person assures him in whom they trust and can believe their arguments. It also resembles the symbolic scheme since the student manipulates mathematical symbols, without understanding their meaning.

Another demonstration scheme to this same proposition can be seen in Figure 2.

The effort on the part of the participant to argue in a coherent manner is highlighted, although some limitations are observed; You understand what you want to express, and you perceive better conceptual mastery. When inquiring about the arguments used, he can explain them and is aware that mathematical results are supported by definitions, axioms, properties and other mathematical results; In addition, it states that, in order to demonstrate, there must be a coherent articulation between these elements.

The procedure fits into analytical proof schemes, as it uses logical deduction to validate the conjecture of both the problem and the proposition (Ceylan & Güler, 2015). The argumentation is transformational because it performs a deductive process that is oriented to defined objectives.

Figure 2.
Act1-1 analytical demonstration scheme.

(i) Si $a+b = -p \wedge ab = q$
 $\rightarrow x^2 + px + q$ polinomio cuadrático
 $\rightarrow x^2 - (a+b)x + ab$
 $\rightarrow x^2 - ax - bx + ab$
 $\rightarrow x^2 - bx - ax + ab$
 $\rightarrow x(x-b) - a(x-b)$
 $\rightarrow (x-a)(x-b) = P(x)$
 Si $P(x) = 0$
 $\rightarrow x = a \vee x = b$
 Por tanto a y b raíces de $P(x)$

Move on to another statement: *Prove or refute the following proposition: if n is a positive integer, then $n^2 + n + 41$ it is a prime number*, one of the students' answers is illustrated in Figure 3. When asking the apprentice for the solution, he says that "I have a hard time doing

this type of problem because in the previous courses I have not had to do demonstrations. The teacher explains the theory, presents without demonstrating most of the results and follows the practice exercises."

Figure 3.
Act1-2 empirical proof scheme.

- Demuestra o refuta la proposición: "Si n es un entero positivo, entonces $n^2 + n + 41$ es un número primo".
 Pregunta: Esto puede ser válido como lematema hasta un punto, para que $n^2 + n + 41$ sea un número primo debe tener un divisor.
 Bueno, primero:
 Si n es un número entero positivo:
 $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$
 eso quiere decir, que n es un número natural
 $n \in \mathbb{N}$
 y n al ser un número natural también puede ser un número primo.

Luego, damos valores a la letra n en la ecuación:
 Cuando $n = 2$
 $(2)^2 + 2 + 41 = 4 + 2 + 41 = 47$
 y el resultado también es un número primo
 pero esto es verdadero hasta el intervalo
 $0 < n < 40 \rightarrow$ números primos.
 Que debe decir $\{2, 3, 5, \dots, 37\}$ porque si intentamos con otro número primo mayor al intervalo, por ejemplo:
 Cuando $n = 41$
 $(41)^2 + 41 + 41 = 1681 + 41 + 41 = 1763$
 el resultado ya no es un número primo.
 Entonces la proposición se contradice porque la ecuación es un número primo con la condición de $0 < n < 40$ y no con todo número primo.

The student's behavior (Figure 3) agrees with the empirical proof schemes of Harel and Sowder (1988), in this case inductive arguments, based on substituting a

mathematical formula and observing a pattern that allows him to generate examples.

5.2. Activity: Equivalence relations

The didactic activity was implemented towards the fifth week of the academic semester, by which time the students already had more experience in the mathematical demonstration techniques, complemented their peers in the structured learning community and their procedures were examined and discussed by their peers or the group in general.

With this activity the congruence module relationship was introduced, its importance,

simplicity and multiple applications in mathematics were highlighted; particularly in number theory, a branch widely related to algebra (Ochoviet, 2014). Next, we present the proposed proof to the propositions: (a) Prove that the modulus congruence m relation is of equivalence and (b) Every integer is congruent modulo m with a single element of the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, m - 1\}$.

Figure 4.

Perceptual (sensory) empirical demonstration scheme Act2-1.

The student argues that he made the demonstration based on what he understood, based on what he had learned in class. It is noted that in the first proposition he mentions the properties that satisfy equivalence relations but does not prove them. As for the second, the student, without justification, makes a mathematical statement: the *congruence module in the integers determines m residual classes of equivalence*; however, it does not prove what was requested.

Because of this, it can be considered that the demonstration scheme offered is empirical, since the source is the inductive reasoning coming from their sensory perceptions, based on their previous knowledge, in this case incipient, with which they intend to validate

(without adequately demonstrating) a result (Sowder and Harel, 1998).

In Figure 5 you can see another of the solutions obtained, this time, its characteristics coincide with the external schemes.

The student states that to build this demonstration he consulted in several sources and that he also asked a classmate who is in a more advanced semester that he had already taken the course with the same teacher. He mentions that the contributions of his peers in the learning community were also important. According to these characteristics, it is an external type of scheme (Harel and Sowder, 1998), since it justifies using arguments of external origin such as books and what an individual who has confidence in his knowledge affirms.

Figure 5.
Act2-1 external demo scheme.

On this same proposition, analytical schemes were also found from the groups articulated

during the work sessions in communities (Figure 6).

Figure 6.
Act2-1 analytical demonstration scheme.

The participants who presented this demonstration were able to explain the whole process. They described that while all members of the learning community consulted together,

in the end they concentrated their efforts to present definitive evidence that was clear and convinced them all.

In the student's response an analytical scheme is appreciated, the demonstration is obtained from the logical deduction (Sowder and Harel, 1998); It is also transformational, since it performs a deductive process of generalization and applies the properties of reflexivity, symmetry and transitivity defined particularly in the congruence relation m modulus.

5.3 Activity: Cyclic groups

The activity was implemented in the eighth week of the semester and, at this point, both individual and community work had been strengthened. Most of the students were aware of the need for interaction between roles, to contribute their ideas and to discuss the

different points of view for the development of the demonstrations.

In this activity, in the proposition *Prove that a cyclic group with a single generator has at most two elements*, a student of the group offers the procedure illustrated in Figure 7, which fits into the empirical schemes, since it is evident that the student seeks certainty and persuasion through direct manipulations of experimental type, based on their conceptions and preconceptions (Harel and Sowder, 1998). In this case, the student uses a mathematical fact based on the concept of greatest common divisor, (mcd) but does not do it correctly. Although it is true that given $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, $mcd(n, n-1) = 1$, your process is not consistent with what you want to demonstrate.

Figure 7.

Empirical demonstration scheme Act3-1.

On the other hand, another of the students presented the following demonstration (Figure 8), which has the characteristics of the external type of scheme. It is evident that the participant found the proof resolved in some physical or

electronic text and copied the translation. In the text is the word since, (enclosed with red in the figure) which is an expression of the English language commonly used to express in demonstrations *since, given that or since*.

Figure 8.
Act3-1 external demonstration scheme.

In addition to the above, the synthesis and deductive logical reasoning used make it clear that they are not the student's own proposals, it is noted that the certainty and persuasion he wants to achieve comes from elements outside his reasoning.

The analytical scheme was also found by other students, in the same activity, but in the statement: *The additive group of the reals $(\mathbb{R}, +)$ is not cyclical*. The development of these allows us to affirm that it is a transformational analytical demonstration scheme (Sowder & Harel, 1998) (Figure 9).

Figure 9.
Act3-1 analytical demonstration scheme.

It is clear that students seek their own conviction and that of others through deductive reasoning: interprets the statement of the proposition, properly uses the concept of generator of a group and its notation; He relates his preconceptions to the approach and in the development makes use of transformations of mathematical objects through logical deduction to arrive, in this case through a contradiction to a negation of the initial assumption.

5.4 Activity: Group homomorphisms

This activity was developed in week 15 of the semester, regarding the last topic discussed in the class of algebraic structures. At this point in the course, the work in the learning communities is consolidated: the students are aware that, through this methodology, their participation and with the contributions of all, the work of the group is enriched and that it is sought to achieve homogeneity in the performance of the participants, while

achieving solidarity coexistence among the members of the community.

Although few, there are still students who remain in empirical demonstration schemes. In this activity it was asked to demonstrate that *the composition of isomorphisms is also an isomorphism*. In the case of the student who

presents the demonstration of Figure 10, his scheme is empirical experimental (Sowder & Harel, 1998); When interviewed, he argues that he did not spend enough time studying the subject and that he was not able to work in his learning community.

Figure 10.

Act4-1 empirical demonstration scheme.

Although the participant makes a true statement that isomorphy between groups is an equivalence relation, inconsistencies in the demonstration process are also evident. It is not clear how the composition of functions is denoted and defined (marked in red in Figure 10), because as it defines the functions $f: G \rightarrow G'$ and $h: G' \rightarrow G''$, the composition is $(h \circ f)(x) = h(f(x))$. Nor does it explain the operations or laws of internal composition of each group, which would strengthen its logical argumentation. In the end you can see the way you force the obtaining of what you want to try.

Another student was found who also presented an empirical proof scheme, this time

of inductive type (Harel & Sowder, 2007), to prove the theorem *Every finite cyclic group of order n is isomorphic to the group of residual classes modulus n : $(\mathbb{Z}_n, \oplus)$* , also arranged in this activity of group homomorphisms.

The apprentice tried to achieve his own certainty and the persuasion of others through manipulations and reasoning by presenting examples and quantitative checks in specific cases (Figure 11). In this case, the student, rather than generalizing, only managed to particularize a situation.

Figure 11.
Empirical demonstration scheme Act4-2.

In Figure 12, we present an external demonstration scheme, of authoritarian type (Harel & Sowder, 1998), in which another student, to demonstrate this same proposition, relies on the arguments he finds in a source

outside him (apparently a textbook) to consolidate the demonstration process, in this way he endorses it and seeks the conviction of others.

Figure 12.
External conviction demonstration scheme Act4-2.

By using this type of argumentation, the student assumes with a certain level of responsibility the development of the demonstration, even though the justification and strategies are not their own. Even the arguments he presents are succinct, imprecise and with them he basically seeks more to fulfill the task than to put his knowledge into action.

The schematic in Figure 13, a demonstration of the same statement on finite cyclic group isomorphism, presented by a group of students working in learning communities, was classified as a transformational analytic demonstration scheme (Ceylon & Güler, 2015).

Figure 12.
Act4-2 analytical demonstration scheme.

③ Todo grupo cíclico finito de orden n es isomorfo al grupo de las clases residuales módulo n : $(\mathbb{Z}_n, +)$.

PLA: Para esta demostración, sea a que el elemento (a) es un generador de G . Entonces:

$$G = \{e, a, a^2, \dots, a^{n-1}\} \dots$$

Luego, se define un $f: \mathbb{Z}_n \rightarrow G$. Lo cual nos dice que:

$$f([i]) = a^i \quad \forall i \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (\text{para todo elemento } a^i \text{ que pertenezca a los } n \text{ divisores})$$

Esto quiere decir, que si f es un isomorfismo. Entonces debemos comprobar en primera instancia que f está bien definido, esto es claro porque si $[i] = [j] \rightarrow a^i = a^j$. Después se supone que esto se cumple para algún $i, j \in \mathbb{Z}$, y por el teorema de la división $j = nk + i$ para cualquier $k \in \mathbb{Z}$.

$a^j = a^{nk+i} = a^{nk} \cdot a^i = (a^n)^k \cdot a^i = e \cdot a^i = a^i$

se cumple Prop. Prop. Prop. Prop. $a^i = e$

Luego de esto, necesitamos probar que f es un isomorfismo, en otras palabras se debe concluir que f es biyectiva y que f preserva la operación del grupo $(\mathbb{Z}_n)$.

que f es biyectiva, esto es muy claro por la definición, digamos:

$$\mathbb{Z}_n = \{[0], [1], [2], [3], \dots, [n-1]\} \quad \text{y}$$

$$G = \{e, a, a^2, a^3, \dots, a^{n-1}\}$$

como se puede observar, ambos grupos se le asigna un elemento "generador" digamos, en G asigna $[0]$ a $e = a^0$, $[1]$ a a^1 , $[2]$ a a^2 , $[3]$ a a^3 y así sucesivamente hasta $[n-1]$ a a^{n-1} . Por último como la operación en $\mathbb{Z}_n$ es la suma, entonces la operación se mantiene.

$f([i] + [j]) = f([i]) \cdot f([j])$ se cumple.

The students transformed the mathematical objects and related the results through a coherent and orderly deductive logical process. Each step is a consequence of the previous one, in addition to what they argue, it is noted that individuals are aware that mathematics is supported by undefined terms and axioms. Because of this, it is possible to consider the schema as a combination of transformational and axiomatic analytical.

5. Conclusions

The learning communities offered a space for inclusive and dynamic participation by all students of the algebraic structures course, in the sense that the difficulties perceived by each member of these became a challenge to overcome together; the committed members of each community were able to interactively enhance their learning (Wenger, 1999).

It was mainly observed that the participation of students in these organizations positively influenced the development of work autonomy, mutual support, the exchange of roles, including research and understanding of most of the

abstract concepts of the course, skills that are indispensable to perform formal demonstration processes in abstract algebra.

Throughout the course, the three demonstration schemes described by Harel and Sowder (1998; 2007) were presented. However, the work in the learning communities favored the progress of the students towards the analytical schemes. The first demonstration processes shown by the students were based on timid efforts to transcribe books or class notes, accompanied by examples, and generalizing with them (authoritarian and empirical inductive external schemes) (Harel & Sowder, 2007). This, to some extent, shows students' lack of confidence in their abilities, under mastery of concepts and inability to reason articulately and logically. However, through the support of their peers in the learning community, mainly when interacting in the presence of the group in general, students left these external ideas to base their approaches on axioms and theorems, to finally deduce their theses logically and formally.

Learning communities allow you to successfully emulate the work of a professional mathematician in the classroom. This promotes the social construction of knowledge (Bleiler-Baxter & Pair, 2017) and allows managing or controlling the presence of internal and external variables to the subject (Bandura, 1976), which covers the cognitive and affective aspects of learning. This is important, because it can be seen as an alternative to traditional techniques that delve into cognitive development but ignore or belittle affective issues.

The results are the product of the answers offered by the participants to the proposed system of activities, the interviews and to what was exposed in the socialization of the tasks. The study focused on analyzing the emerging demonstration schemes when working in abstract algebra and the incidence of work in learning communities in these. Therefore, the proposals chosen for the activities were arbitrary and it is possible to change them according to the learning objectives. Other researchers may decide activities to theorize differently in research with similar instructional structures.

Finally, the progress made with the participants is highlighted and it is recommended to pay attention when students are encouraged to prove theorems individually, since their process can be strengthened with work in learning communities. Positive changes have been evidenced in confidence, affective and academic performance, which influences the development of their mathematical thinking (Bandura, 1976; Wenger, McDermott & Snyder, 2002; Campbell & Lee, 2017). Consistent with this, it is recommended to conduct more similar research in other areas of mathematics categorized by students as difficult in university curricula, such as real, functional, and complex analysis.

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